

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

INTERPRETATION OF THE "TEACHING STRATEGIES BLOCK" OF THE MATHEMATICS SUBJECT CURRICULUM AT THE GENERAL EDUCATION LEVEL BASED ON THE "SYSTEM-STRUCTURE" APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

In the article, it is emphasized that the curriculum reform is conditioned by the need to ensure the adequacy of the implementation of education in Azerbaijan to the demands of the 21st century, to cultivate a creative, self-developing personality, and the content of the abilities that must be transformed into the subject of a student who has completed his general education is shown.

The significance of the educator's reference to the "system-structure" approach in the research work both in familiarizing himself with the essence of the "General Education Program" and in his practical activities related to its implementation, the relevance of subject-oriented curricula to the content of the science field, and its perfect system of concepts, directly related to these concepts. it is drawn to the center of attention directed to its absorption.

In the article, 1) principles of the pedagogical process, 2) planning of training on the subject, 3) forms and methods (methods) used in the organization of training, 4) content, which are included in the "Teaching strategies" block of the "block-scheme" form of the structure of the Mathematics subject curriculum at the general education level. Interpretation and generalizations are presented based on the "system-structure" dialectical approach, which aims to reveal the nature of the subsystems in order to benefit the educator at the desired level in the organization and management of the real pedagogical process from the comments and instructions related to the standards.

Keywords: Educational program; curriculum; subject curriculum; "block-scheme" form of the curriculum; learning strategies; completeness; equal opportunities; supportive environment; teaching unit; teaching situation; research question; motivation; information exchange; reflection; business forms; work with groups; creative application.

Relevance of the research topic. Observations show that mistakes are made in the activities of educators in the application of Mathematics subject curriculum at the general education level. This has a negative effect on the efficiency level of the teaching process of Mathematics.

It is undeniable that the level of understanding of any real existence (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of taking advantage of it in adequate directions. On the basis of our scientific observations conducted over the past ten years (at the stage of applying a new approach to the philosophy of general education in Azerbaijan), we have come to the conclusion that in the process of using the subject curricula (including the Mathematics subject curriculum), the errors manifested in the activities of the educators are based on a number of reasons, as well as the subject curriculum its essence is not sufficiently honestly understood by these subjects. Based on our experience of scientific activity, we claim that the "system-structure" approach (the idea of L. Bertalanf, which is the basis of system analysis [14;8]) is the understanding of any objective reality (material or spiritual), it is the most reliable dialectical method to get to its essence, in other words, it is a way of spiritual exploration (it is essentially a form of cognitive movement). The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method is not used enough in the theoretical and

technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the mathematics subject curriculum and the determination of its application ways. Therefore, we recommend that only one of the many issues that lead to the solution of the problem, which is the basis for the manifestation of the above-mentioned error, is formulated as "Interpretation of the "Teaching strategies" block elements" of the Mathematics subject curriculum at the general education level based on the "system-structure" approach" and its actual research we claim to be the subject. is essentially a form of cognitive action). The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method is not used enough in the theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the mathematics subject curriculum and the determination of its application ways. Therefore, we recommend that only one of the many issues that lead to the solution of the problem, which is the basis for the manifestation of the above-mentioned error, is formulated as "Interpretation of the "Teaching strategies" block elements" of the Mathematics subject curriculum at the general education level based on the "system-structure" approach" and its actual research we claim to be the subject. is essentially a form of cognitive action). The analysis of the materials we have collected gives reason to say that this method is not used enough in the theoretical and technological directions regarding the discovery of the essence of the

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Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of research materials.

It is known that in the 21st century, the main value in the life and development of both society and each of its members is a creative, self-developing personality. [12; 16] Education also cannot exist outside the realities of a changing world. Modern psychology considers the creation of favorable conditions for the discovery and realization of the child's creative abilities as the main goal of education [4; 290-292]. Therefore, since the main value in the modern period is a creative, self-developing personality, the educational process should form creativity and self-development abilities in the child. This, in turn, is based on the following activity, the need to understand and the abilities: 1) logical thinking; 2) critical approach to objects and events of the surrounding world; 3) independent decision-making; 4) change the surroundings at a creative speed; 5) independent acquisition of knowledge; 6) solving practical problems; 7) setting new goals for personality development.

The general learning results of a student who has completed his general education are formed as a synthesis and dialectical unification of the results targeted in the teaching process of all subjects (including mathematics) taught in general education schools.

It is undeniable that it is of particular importance for the mathematics teacher to honestly know the tasks

set before the general education (general expected results). However, this is one side of the issue and it is necessary to put the activity related to the educational process into a result-oriented system. Thus, the goal is the system-creating component of the activity. At the same time, it is very important to implement the training process in what content, based on what strategy, based on what evaluation mechanisms, in order to achieve the goal. "The new necessary minimum of training at the levels of general education, the level of knowledge, the general learning results for the subject and the connection of the skills to be acquired with the learning results that will be obtained in separate levels of general education is considered one of the most important problems of education" [9; 71].

The teacher should be able to find both theoretical and practical answers to all questions related to the learning process. He should know which model he uses in the process of which he is a facilitator and what are the specific features of this model. This model incorporates the superior merits of traditional models (it should not be forgotten that innovation is not a complete denial of the old, such a denial can bring more harm than good) and what success it promises to the real pedagogical process. The interpretation of the main features of the educational program (curriculum) [5; 228-229] based on the "system-structure" approach, which is currently applied in general education schools "perceived as a conceptual barrier that enables the effective organization of all activities related to the educational process, purposeful and consistent implementation" giving is for the benefit of the common cause.

The teacher is one of the subjects of the "enabling function" in the implementation of the educational program. The level of his penetration into the essence of the mentioned program has a conditioning effect on the effectiveness of its activity. Therefore, it is important to refer to the "system-structural approach" both in getting to know the essence of the program and in the practical activities related to its implementation, the analysis of research materials and our work experience brings us to this conclusion.

It should be emphasized here that the essence of the system is determined by its structure and function, that is, by the nature of the relationship between the elements and their behavior, and by the specificity of the relationship between the object and the conditions. Without studying the elements that make up the system and their mutual influence, it is impossible to distinguish the continuous, important and necessary relationships here. Such continuous, important and necessary interaction of elements characterizes the structure of the system. The law of relationships of structural elements acts as an invariant of the system. Without learning and opening the relationship of the elements with the whole formed by them, both the function of the system and the functions of each element with regard to the whole remain in the shadows. The full concept is understood in terms of the system, it is the organization of that system. Each system has its own structure and the function that this structure carries. A system can be viewed as a whole consisting of the unity of its structure and function. Systems differ from each other not only

by their structure and functions, but also mainly by the nature of the unity of structure and function, the nature of this unity.

The educational program (curriculum) determines the content of education and the rules of mastering it for different levels of education in accordance with state educational standards [6; 106-107]. The educational program includes the curriculum, educational programs for subjects, recommendations on methodical provision, assessment and other relevant educational technologies [5; 173].

Educational curricula are divided into two parts, productive and personality-oriented according to their nature: 1) Science-oriented curricula cover the field of science and its perfect system of concepts by content and are directly directed to mastering these concepts. 2) Personality-oriented curricula are distinguished by giving priority to life skills and habits. "Personality-oriented", "pupil-oriented" and "result-oriented" approaches of the curriculum show that the student is at

the center of the learning process"[11]. These approaches are reflected, in particular, in the writing of learning objectives. The highlighted features of the curriculum have a great benefit in the educational process: it makes the educational process more efficient, it enables the formation of experience-oriented skills. In this regard, new demands are placed on the teacher [1; 174].

Subject curricula: take a balanced and comprehensive approach to learning different skills; enables achievement of content standards using active learning methods; implies constant assessment of students' knowledge and understanding, making corrections during the academic year; ensures the involvement of students in training, preparation and motivation for continuous education; it envisages the use of modern technologies while studying, evaluating students' knowledge, improving their literacy; has adequate training resources and administrative support.[2; 158-161]

The block diagram form of the subject curriculum structure can be drawn as follows [7; 38]:

"Revealing the child's creative abilities and realizing them, creating favorable conditions for the formation of his personality is one of the main goals of education" [7; 290-292]. There is no doubt that subjects, which are the main enabling components of the implementation of general education, are of high value as an important tool in the formation of the personality of schoolchildren. The "enabling" functions of the subjects are expressed in the "Education Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan" in the following content:

- ensures that students are taught the basics of science, inculcated the necessary knowledge, skills and habits, prepare them for life and work;

- enables physical and intellectual development of students, acquisition of necessary knowledge, formation of civic thinking based on healthy lifestyle and

civilized values, inculcation of respect for national and worldly values, determination of rights and responsibilities in front of family, society, state and environment[2; 21-23].

Based on the official state documents, we can say that "... the content of general education subjects aims at the following iyearxic goals by focusing on different levels of education":

- to improve reading, writing and calculation skills in primary education, to form basic knowledge about man, society and nature, elements of logical thinking, aesthetic and artistic taste and other characteristics;

- oral speech and writing culture, communication skills, cognitive activity, the development of logical thinking, the formation of relevant knowledge and

ideas about the subjects included in the educational program as well as the development of world civilization, the ability to use modern information and communication tools, events to provide the ability to evaluate and determine their own future directions of action;

- realization of talents and abilities, preparation for independent life and professional choice, formation of an active citizen position, respect for national and universal values, human rights and freedoms and tolerance, free use of modern information and communication technologies and other technical means, acquiring the basics of economic knowledge, communicating in one or more foreign languages, etc. provide (see [2] for more information).

In the mentioned system of knowledge, skills and habits, what is obtained at different educational levels in the teaching of Mathematics is included as a component, which can be interpreted as follows can be: 1) At the primary education level, it is ensured that students perform calculations, master written and oral calculation algorithms, calculate numerical expressions, solve textual problems, have basic measurement habits, spatial and geometric concepts, classify given data, and have mathematical knowledge habits to apply in daily life are formed; 2) Solving daily life problems at the secondary education level, studying other relevant subjects, continuing education in profiled classes, acquiring mathematical knowledge necessary for secondary education in other forms, forming a way of thinking that lays the groundwork for students' intellectual development and successful practical activities, creating a complete understanding of the exceptional importance of mathematics in the development of civilization and society as an organic part of universal culture, students in the field of mathematics acquiring appropriate skills in accordance with their age, logically understanding and analyzing knowledge of various forms and contents, the essence of the probability nature of random events in life understanding is ensured; 3) Inculcation of new concepts and essences, more systematic and application-oriented practical habits, enrichment of speech by developing mathematical language, assimilation of mathematical knowledge that lays the groundwork for continuing future education and professional activities through the expansion and development of activities determined at the secondary education level. , formation of algorithmic culture is ensured. [5; 57]

A student who has completed general education is expected to become a subject of the following general results: performs algorithms related to mathematical materials, uses mathematical concepts and formulas in real life; determines the relationship between quantities based on the generalization of special cases and experiences and expresses them in mathematical language; uses algebraic transformations and functional dependencies in the study of related subjects and in the investigation of existing regularities of the surrounding world; uses expanded spatial concepts in drawing, pictures and schemes, describing objects in the surrounding world; explains information about the existence of probability and statistical regularities in the surrounding world, predicts the occurrence of events based on

the classical model of probability; uses measurement and calculation tools, performs written and oral operations; bases his judgments with mathematical facts and interprets his logical results, distinguishes proven hypothesis from assumptions [8; 64].

The "Teaching strategies" block covers the forms, methods and techniques used by the teacher in the teaching process. It should be noted that until this time, the concept of "teaching strategies" was not used in the Azerbaijani pedagogical literature. However, recently, during the period of educational reform, the concept of "educational strategy" has started to be addressed when preparing subject curricula[5; 280]. Developing the concept of learning strategies in new subject curricula and using it more effectively in the organization of the pedagogical process requires, first of all, the explanation of education as one of the main pedagogical concepts in terms of modern requirements. The "Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on Education" stipulates that education is systematized (according to the interests of the state, society, individual - italics are ours) knowledge, skills, is the process of acquiring habits and its result. [2; 6]. Scientific sources emphasize that education should be treated not only as a result or just a process, but as a way of expression with broader shades of meaning. "Especially the personality-oriented nature of education requires to approach it from several positions: education is a value; education is a system; education is a process; education is the result". [13;115]. We completely agree with this opinion.

First of all, education is viewed as a value that includes language, mentality, national skills, customs and traditions. In the formation of these values, personality orientation, culture, collectivism, systematicity, and integrity act as leading principles. Education, which has its own system, exists in stages. These stages, which differ in their expected results, complement each other and form a general system of education by being sequentially arranged. At this time, democratization, humanization, differentiation, individualization, socialization, diversity and inclusiveness play a key role as leading principles. Education is also treated as a process, since it continuously encompasses the acquisition of universal and national values in the process of socialization. Its didactic basis is relevance to nature, practicality, directionality, variability, gradual, consideration of individual needs and continuity. Education is viewed as a result, as it is the conclusion of teacher and student activities as a whole. It is evaluated as the end of a whole one-stage process. [5; 280]

Among the elements contained in the "Education strategies" block, "Description of the main requirements for the organization of training on the subject" has a special place. It is necessary to follow the important requirements-didactic principles in the proper construction of the pedagogical process. In the organization of the pedagogical process in accordance with the currently applied curricula in the general education system, it is considered necessary to take principles such as 1) completeness of the pedagogical process, 2) creation of equal opportunities in training, 3) student orientation, 4) development orientation, 5) stimulation of activity, 6) creation of a supportive environment.

Among the elements contained in the "Teaching strategies" block, "Teaching planning by subject" has a special place. Creating annual planning is the most important task facing educators. Planning is the direction of action of teachers to determine the main goals and achieve them. The annual planning shows when and in what order the teaching unit will teach.

In scientific sources, it is recommended to expect the following sequence of subject planning: 1. To determine the educational units to be implemented based on the content standards; 2. Determine the principle of sequence of teaching units; 3. Allocate time according to the curriculum for each educational unit; 4. To take into account student interests in each case. [5; 281]

The main documents used in the annual planning process are: content standards; assessment standards; education plan; textbook; methodological tool for the teacher. In particular, let's emphasize that during the preparation of the calendar plan, the weeks of the school year, important events that will take place in the school year (historical days), the name of the study units and the subjects included in them are determined. The content standards (sub-standards) to be realized through each educational unit and topic are selected, the resources to be used are determined, and the time allotted for each topic is noted. Based on the model annual planning, the teacher individually prepares a daily or weekly lesson plan.

According to the descriptive scheme of the mathematics subject curriculum, in the "Teaching strategies" block, the "element acting as a central link" is the form and methods (methods) of the organization of training.

Despite the fact that the clear understanding of the concept of "Teaching method", which is one of the important elements of the "Teaching strategies" system, and the discovery of its essence have important theoretical and practical importance, the debates among didactics in this direction have been going on for a long time [11]. In our opinion, the training method is a system of rules aimed at solving the educational, educational and developmental tasks set in the training process, determined by the principles derived from the regularities of training, and ensuring the dialectical unity of the activities of teachers and students (a component of the training process).

Since the standards are result-oriented and student-oriented, it is considered appropriate to use active learning methods in their implementation. Characteristic features of active learning methods include: 1) First of all, attention is paid to the formation of the student's personality; 2) The teacher acts as a coordinator of training activities, a consultant and an assistant of students; 3) Students become active researchers in the process of problem solving; 4) Knowledge and skills are acquired independently by students; 5) Conditions for cooperation between teacher-student and student-student are created; 6) The integrative organization of lessons is preferred; 7) The application of non-standard lessons is given wide scope [5; 286-287]

Training practice has confirmed that the main organizational form of training and education work in secondary schools is the lesson. The improvement of educational material, which contains a part of human

social experience, and educational methods aimed at its mastery, conditions the modernization of their form of existence (educational material and methods for the lesson act together in the place of content) (turning into a suitable way of existence) (such is the dialectical dependence between form and content). Therefore, in addition to "traditional lesson", "modern lesson", "developing lesson", "problematic lesson", "phased lesson", "synthetic lesson", "active lesson" etc. Concepts reflecting the quality characteristics of the lesson were used from time to time, and scientific comments were given to them. With intense pedagogical, psychological, methodological research, the "modern lesson" model was created and the era (the current century,

The word "modern" in the sense of "modern lesson" has a unique heuristic meaning. "Modern lesson" does not mean "today's lesson". A lesson based on the successes of the time is called a modern lesson. In this sense, they usually distinguish two aspects that are organically connected with each other. Often, when they say modern lesson, they understand it not only to raise the scientific-theoretical level of the lesson, to modernize it. The lesson should reflect the achievements of the time according to its scientific and theoretical level. This is without a doubt. However, it would be one-sided to explain the meaning of modern lessons only in this root. We are talking about a pedagogical phenomenon. The word "modern" characterizes the lesson. This is true both from a psychological and pedagogical point of view, and from a linguistic point of view. The lesson becomes modern not only due to its scientific-theoretical level, but also due to its pedagogical concept - it is built with new pedagogical thinking dimensions [7; 36-37]

The attitude of the student to the content and tools of the training material can be manifested as stationary or problematic. Therefore, depending on the stationarity or problem, the student's thought movement is re-productive or productive. In the forms of organization of training, the content of the training material and the methods of action adequate to it appear in the place of the content. Therefore, the substructures of the forms of organization of training and their relationship remain in the monopoly of the relationship between the student's analytical and heuristic activities. The basis of the pedagogical (external), mental (internal) and methodical inter-structural relations of the organizational form is also the relation between the students' analytical and heuristic activities. The relationship between the degree of pedagogical influence in the training process and the student's internal activity and independence reflects the nature of his (student's) activity. At present, the approach to this process as a field of activity aimed at developing the human personality has begun to prevail. This did not remain unaffected by the forms of education, views on its organization, and directions for improvement. In our modern time, the idea of active (interactive) learning has gained a superior position due to the above-mentioned effects. By the way, let's emphasize that " In our modern time, the idea of active (interactive) learning has gained a superior position due to the above-mentioned effects. By the way, let's empha-

size that "In our modern time, the idea of active (interactive) learning has gained a superior position due to the above-mentioned effects. By the way, let's emphasize that "modern lesson" organization form of active (interactive) training active lesson "is used as a synonym for the concept.

The paradigms of the lesson, which is the organizational form of that model (the way of implementing education), are: Approach to learners as subjects; Dialogical approach; Existentiality (consideration of the integrity of human nature); Integrativeness; Providing a developmental character; Formation of pedagogical personnel at a level that meets modern requirements; The fundamentality of the teaching-learning process; The nature of the training is "subject-subject" ("S-S"); Activity of the participants during the whole lesson; Creating a problem situation at the beginning of the lesson and focusing its course on solving the problem; Conducting the lesson in the form of research; Directing students to independent discovery of new knowledge through thought-provoking and guiding questions; Conducting the lesson in the form of dialogue; Regular existence of mutual cooperation and feedback between teachers and students; Wide use of group work, joint activity of students; Diversity and novelty of training tools and tasks; Use of worksheets; Creative application of knowledge, etc.

Among the elements included in the structure of the lesson, which is the main organizational form of active (interactive) training, are: 1) Motivation (posing a problem, putting forward hypotheses); 2) Conducting research (searching for facts to test hypotheses); 3) Information exchange (presentation of obtained data and student research); 4) Discussion and organization of information (discussion of obtained information, coordination of various facts, their systematization); 5) Generalization and drawing conclusions (generalizations, comparison of results with hypotheses and conclusion about their confirmation or refutation, answer to the research question); 6) Productive (creative) application (application in new conditions, solving practical issues); 7) Evaluation or reflection (inspection and evaluation of personal activity - this can be done at any stage).

The structure of the active lesson reminds of the stages of the research process (the main shade of the learning process is research). In an active lesson, new information is obtained through the student himself (as a result of research). The stage of application in an active lesson is creative in nature. One of the special stages of the active lesson is the reflection stage. As a result of reflection, the student understands the main stages of his research activity.

Learning success is determined not only by the student's ability to learn, overall abilities, etc., but also by learning motivation. In other words, for him to "read well", along with all other conditions, it is necessary to form learning motivation.

Motivation is an important component in an active lesson - it is a process that activates the thinking process and stimulates the cognitive activity of students.. The existence of this process is determined by components such as goal, need, personal meaning, motive.

The motivation phase consists of the following parts: A question or task is formulated to pose the problem; Questions are suggested; Assumptions are made.

Among the factors that create motivation are the following: A problem situation that creates various assumptions; Features of the object (unusuality, free thinking and interesting feature); Availability of research; The possibility of creativity. [10; 258]. Motivation is mainly based on two principles: 1) problematic; 2) purposefulness. Motivation should be consistent with the learning outcomes of the lesson. Before building the motivation, "Substandards" and then "Learning outcomes of the lesson" should be defined. The research question arises as a result of the motivation. Motivation can be short and gradual. A short motivation consists of only one research question. Staged motivation includes at least two stages.

Guiding questions, tasks are focused on learning outcomes, influencing factors are further strengthened for students to become active carriers of the lesson. To formulate a research question, the teacher must first identify the summary at the end of the lesson. The motivation phase ends with the hypotheses put forward according to the research question. It is important to return to it at the end of the lesson. As a result of motivation, the research question should serve the learning outcomes. In this process, the topic of the lesson plays only the role of a tool. Although the topic is a tool, in certain cases it can influence the content of the motivation.

The purpose of "Information exchange", one of the concluding stages of the active lesson, is to familiarize all students with new facts and findings. Information sharing can only be effective if the class is focused on active listening and feedback.

"Discussion and organization of information" The next step is to systematize knowledge based on new facts and uncovering the key relationship to answer the research question. It is clear that the material that the teacher has to work with is detailed. He must try to connect these scattered facts to discover the main unifying idea and pattern. In that time period, comparison, analysis and synthesis are used. Let us emphasize that the choice here depends on the content of the material and the purpose of the research.

"Deriving conclusions, justifying generalization" is one of the structural elements of the lesson. After generalization, it is necessary to compare the formed idea with the research question and initial hypotheses.

In the implementation of the mathematics subject curriculum, daily planning for each active lesson system is also an element to be focused on. It is useful to include the following in daily planning: 1) Determine the expected results of the lesson (determine the learning results of the lesson based on the sub-standard); 2) Determine what conclusions (generalizations) students will come to at the end of the lesson; 3) Preparing the motivation of the lesson (creating a problem situation, choosing the type of motivation, setting the research question correctly); 4) Identify the sources of knowledge used to collect new knowledge during research; 5) Prepare research tasks that can lead to the

specified expected results; 6) Determine research methods; 7) Prepare the necessary materials and worksheets, determine the presentation form of the research; 8) To express guiding questions used during the discussion; 9) Systematization of information (scheme, formula, graph, table, project, etc.); 10) To prepare additional information, tasks, taking into account the assumed new results; 11) Determine the time for each stage of the lesson; 12) Prepare tasks for the creative application stage; 13) Choosing the evaluation form (method), defining the criteria; 14) Determine the course of reflection based on the needs of teachers and students; 15) Determine the technical means to be used in the lesson; 16) Prepare stationery to be used in the lesson. [5; 286] 15) Determine the technical means to be used in the lesson; 16) Prepare stationery to be used in the lesson. [5; 286] 15) Determine the technical means to be used in the lesson; 16) Prepare stationery to be used in the lesson. [5; 286]

Individual, pair, large and small group work is included among the forms of organization of students' educational activities (work forms) included in the "Teaching strategies" block. Work with small groups and pairs are considered active forms of learning. During the organization of group work, the teacher's and students' observance of certain rules has a positive effect on the effectiveness of the work, which are presented in the following aspects in scientific sources: 1. Aspects related to the teacher's organizational activity: 1) Accurately measuring the organization of the work: goals, determine the plan and duration of work; 2) Preparation of necessary materials for group work (tasks for group work, worksheets, etc.); 3) Predetermine the method of dividing into groups according to the objectives of the lesson; 4) Divide and place participants into groups; 5) Correctly divide the duties of group members; 6) Provide accurate information on the performance of the work and write it on the board (or other means); 7) To define (or remember) the rules of group work; 8) Create conditions for the exchange stage of group work results; 9) Bringing the evaluation criteria to the attention of the participants. 2. Aspects related to the teacher's behavioral activity. 1) Identifying and controlling the work of groups; 2) If necessary, intervene in the work of students, identify problems arising in the process of group work in a timely manner and provide assistance in solving those problems; 3) Asking guiding questions to students, directing them to search; 4) Answering students' questions, paying more attention to weak students; 5) Answering the questions of group members, helping those who have difficulties;

It is attributed by students to the organizational aspect of group work: 1) Correctly divide the tasks of group members; 2) Correctly identify group leaders; 3) Effective use of time. Behavioral aspects of group work are attributed by students: 1) To be active during group work; 2) Fulfill the obligation and take responsibility for one's behavior; 3) Listening carefully to each other; 3) To work together, to cooperate, to help and support each other; 4) Collectively help the group to successfully achieve its goals; 5) To express one's point of view; 6) Respect each other's ideas; 7) To confirm one's thoughts and ideas with knowledge (facts); 8) To help

create an environment of pleasant relations, not to allow personal criticism, negative comments and insults; 9) Avoid conflict, compete in the positive sense of the word; 10) Looking for compromise ways when solving the problem; 11) Do not allow extraneous conversations, talk on the topic given by the teacher; 12) Observing discipline during work; 13) To obey the rules of group work. (See [15] for more information).

A key component of active/interactive learning that emphasizes constructivism and cooperativism, which we consider as a subsystem of an excellent learning system. It is useful for the teacher to wait for the rules of facilitation in the implementation of the guidance position as his special function (for more information, see: [10; 255])

Note that the facility cooperation of teachers and students, mutual respect and trust of teachers and students, acceptance of students as they are and their constant support by the teacher; confidence in students' abilities, stimulation of thinking; it is based on the creation of learning stimulus and motivation in students, their adaptation to the classroom environment, and the special sensitive attitude of the teacher. It must be accepted that facilitation: is the process of organizing, activating and effectively directing the discussion in the group; the feature of the facilitation process is that the information is not delivered by the facilitator, but by the group; the position of the facilitator, its main function is to provoke thought and direct it in the necessary direction; the facilitation approach is to focus on the full satisfaction of cognitive and creative needs, that is, on students realizing their abilities; the teacher-facilitator acts as a guide in the process of acquiring knowledge by the child. [15]

The document containing the interpretation of the content standards is one of the important elements included in the "Teaching strategies" block. It is emphasized in scientific sources that the content standard is the state requirement set for the level of knowledge and skills of the student [5; 468]. The subject standards cover the content that is important for all students within the secondary education course, describe the students' comprehension abilities, knowledge and skills, determine the issues that every student in the country can and should study in the subject, and prepare students for the next level of secondary education.

The new approach to setting the content of the standards envisages that each standard consists of several defined objectives (sub-standards) and is repeated throughout the grades in an appropriately expanding capacity. The components of teaching and mastering the relevant subject are not isolated from each other, they must be connected and complement each other.

The function of the core standard is to explain the defined learning outcomes in a general way along the content lines. It is related to the functions of sub-standards: it creates a reliable basis for the precise determination of learning objectives; plays an important role in the correct selection of training strategies; ensures integration in training; ensures continuous development of training content; provides summative assessment for classes and subjects.

Scientific novelty and theoretical significance of the research work.

1) The importance of the application of the "system-structure" approach method, which was formed as an important branch of the dialectic regarding the discovery of the essence of the subject curriculum (specifically the mathematics subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods), was brought to the attention of the researchers; 2) The discovery of the essence of the mathematics subject curriculum at the general education level and its application the solution of one of the cognitive issues that determines the solution of the problem of processing in the optimal version - the interpretation of the "learning strategies block elements" based on the "system-structure" approach" was presented.

Practical significance of the research work.

We hope that the solution of one of the important cognitive issues that determines the solution to the problem of uncovering the essence of this or that subject curriculum (as well as the Mathematics subject curriculum) applied at the General Education level and its application in the optimal version - on the basis of the "system-structure" approach of the "Teaching strategies block elements" "interpretation" will have a positive effect on the formation of an environment for the elimination of errors manifested in the activities of educators in the application of the mathematics subject curriculum.

The result.

1) The level of understanding of any real existence (objective existence) has a determining effect on the results of taking advantage of it in adequate directions; 2) In the application of any subject curriculum (as well as the Mathematics subject curriculum) at the general education level, making mistakes in the activity of educators has a negative effect on the efficiency level of the teaching process of this subject; 3) In the process of using the mathematics subject curriculum, at the basis of the mistakes manifested in the activity of practical educators, there is a lack of honest enough understanding of its essence by these subjects; 4) "system-structure" approach to the essence of understanding any existing things is the most reliable dialectical method of arriving; 5) The dialectical method of "system-structure" approach regarding the discovery of the essence of the mathematics subject curriculum and the determination of its application methods was not used in theoretical and technological directions; 6) One of the cognitive issues aimed at solving the problem that creates the basis for the manifestations of the error caused by the "gap" regarding the discovery of the essence of the mathematics subject curriculum and the determination of the

ways of its application is "Interpretation of the "Teaching strategies block elements" of the mathematics subject curriculum at the general education level based on the "system-structure" approach" and our research summary presented in this direction benefits the teaching process of this or that subject.

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